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Process design and simulation of the HERCCULES solvent-based post-combustion CO₂ capture pilot for cement plants

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Abstract

This work presents the design of a solvent-based post-combustion CO₂ capture pilot to be tested on real cement flue gases. The pilot plant, employing solvent-based CO₂ absorption/stripping in packed columns, has been designed to capture and produce 3 t per day of high purity liquid CO₂ from a slip stream of flue gases from a cement kiln. Process design is performed via Aspen Plus V14 simulations considering 30% w/w aqueous MEA as chemical solvent. More than 10 configurations featuring several modifications to the standard post-combustion process have been evaluated and characterized in terms of equivalent energy consumption. The process configuration featuring the integration of absorber intercooling, rich solvent split and lean vapor recompression is one of the most energy efficient and it reports a substantial reduction (18% savings) in the equivalent energy consumption compared to the conventional CO₂ capture MEA process.

Keywords: Pilot plant; Process simulation; Post-combustion CO₂ capture; Process modifications; Equivalent power consumption; CO₂ capture with solvents; HERCCULES;

1. Introduction

In the EU HORIZON HERCCULES project (www.herccules.eu) different pilot plant configurations will be studied for cement decarbonization at TRL 7. The first one will be a post-combustion capture (PCC) pilot to test different process configurations and solvents for CO₂ capture on real cement flue gases. This paper presents the process design and simulation of the PCC demonstration unit based on chemical absorption with solvents, designed by Tecno Project Industriale (TPI) and Politecnico di Milano (POLIMI) to capture 3 t per day of CO₂ with 30%w MEA solution and a target capture rate of 95% from a cement plant in Italy owned by Buzzi. The capture plant is flexible since it can be operated under different process configurations (intercooled absorber, solvent split, lean vapor compression, stripper operating from 1 to 3.5 bar(a)) and can test a membrane contactor unit in absorption mode. A detailed process flow diagram of the HERCCULES post-combustion CO₂ capture pilot plant is illustrated in Fig 1. This design is a result of a process simulation analysis in which several modifications to the conventional PCC concept have been investigated with Aspen Plus, after selecting them based on a literature analysis [1–4]. The adopted process variants

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to the conventional configuration include absorber intercooling (INT), Rich Solvent Split (RSS), Higher Pressure stripper (HP), Lean Vapor reCompression (LVC), Stripper Overhead Compression (SOC) and some combinations of them.

The study presented in this work is focused on identifying the most promising process configuration in terms of overall energy performance calculated based on process simulations. The experimental campaigns scheduled in 2025 will allow validating the model and optimizing the process based on field data, finding the best operative conditions and configuration and studying the solvent interaction with real flue gases.

Fig. 1. Process Flow Diagram of the HERCCULES amine-based post-combustion CO₂ capture demonstration plant.

Nomenclature

COP	Coefficient Of Performance
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
L/R	Lean/Rich
MEA	Monoethanolamine
SRD	Specific Reboiler Duty
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

2. Methodology

A detailed Aspen Plus flowsheet of the post-combustion capture process has been developed starting from previous literature studies and the process simulation validated against experimental literature data from the 30%w/w MEA-based pilot plant campaigns of Technology Centre Mongstad (TCM)[5], National Carbon Capture Centre (NCCC)[6] and Kaiserslautern lab-scale facility[7].

By means of the Aspen Plus model, entailing validated thermodynamics and kinetics for the rate-based columns, the different configurations for the PCC pilot plant have been simulated. The application features the standard packed absorption/stripping CO₂ capture process based on chemical absorption with an aqueous solution of 30%w/w MEA, still considered to be the benchmark chemical solvent for CO₂ capture. Besides the two main columns (absorber and

stripper), the pilot also envisages a direct contact cooler (DCC), a water wash section and the CO₂ compression and liquefaction stage, to produce liquid CO₂ with a purity greater than 99.9%mol.

Real plant data on flue gas compositions, temperature and pressure provided by the industrial partners of the HERCCULES project have been used as input to the process simulation. Flue gases are extracted before the main stack (right after the bag filter but before being diluted by the clinker cooler air) and the nominal flow rate sent to the pilot is 308 Nm³/h with an average CO₂ molar content of 20.4%mol. Other input parameters and assumptions for the Aspen Plus simulation involve the packing type and height of the columns, the CO₂ lean loading of the solvent (0.2 mol_{CO₂}/mol_{MEA}) and the minimum temperature difference in the lean-rich heat exchanger (10 °C), while the columns are sized to have an approach to flooding lower than 80%. A summary of the basis of design for the HERCCULES PCC pilot plant is reported in Table 1 for the base case without any process modifications. Starting from the base case, several modifications and integrations have been simulated, aiming at reducing the energy penalty of the capture process:

- Absorber intercooling: two interstage coolers to cool down to 40 °C the liquid phase at some specific packing heights (3 and 6 m from the bottom).
- Rich solvent split: part of the rich solution by-passes the L/R heat exchanger (15% considered in this study) and is injected at the top of the stripper, while the hot rich stream enters at a lower injection point.
- High pressure stripper operation: stripper and reboiler are operated at higher pressure compared to the standard process.
- Lean vapor recompression: the lean solution from the stripper is flashed and the vapor that is generated is recompressed into the stripper bottom.
- Stripper overhead compression: the vapor stream leaving the top of the stripper is compressed before water condenser to use the heat of condensation and heat of compression as additional heat sources in the reboiler.

Table 1: Basis of design of the HERCCULES post-combustion CO₂ capture pilot plant for cement.

Model input parameters and assumptions	
Flue gas feed flow rate, Nm ³ /h	308
Flue gas inlet temperature (upstream DCC), °C	95
Lean solvent temperature, °C	35
CO ₂ inlet gas concentration, %mol	20.4%
N ₂ inlet gas concentration, %mol	57.4%
H ₂ O inlet gas concentration, %mol	13%
O ₂ inlet gas concentration, %mol	9.2%
CO ₂ lean loading, mol _{CO₂} /mol _{MEA}	0.2
Absorber packing height, m	12
Absorber diameter, m	0.35
Absorber packing type	FLEXIPAC 350X
Minimum ΔT _{in} Lean/Rich HX, °C	10
Stripper packing type	INTALOX-N
Stripper packing height, m	5.5
Stripper diameter, m	0.31
Stripper operating pressure, bar	2.1

The energy efficiency of the process is evaluated in terms of specific equivalent electrical power consumption ($\dot{w}_{eq}, kWh/tCO_2$). This quantity allows a more thermodynamically consistent comparison of cases with different electricity and thermal power consumption, since the thermal power for solvent regeneration is converted to an equivalent electricity consumption via a specific conversion coefficient. \dot{w}_{eq} is estimated with the expression reported in Eq. 1, which includes the equivalent electric reboiler duty, the electricity consumption for solvent and water pumps, flue gas fan, CO₂ compression and liquefaction unit and, if present, LVC/SOC compressors.

$$\dot{w}_{eq}[kWh/tCO_2] = \dot{w}_{eq,reb} + \dot{w}_{pump \& fan} + \dot{w}_{CO_2 compr \& liq} + \dot{w}_{LVC/SOC} \quad (1)$$

To calculate the equivalent electricity consumption from the reboiler, the ratio between electric and thermal power is assumed to be equal to 0.5. This value is consistent with a reference electric-driven heat pump system with a COP of 2 [8].

3. Process simulation results

Table 2 reports the main process simulation outcomes for the base case (i.e. conventional configuration with adiabatic absorber), where all the rich solvent passes through the L/R heat exchanger and is injected at the top of the stripper and the reboiler is fed by steam and operates at 2.1 bar. For a CO₂ capture efficiency of 95.2%, a CO₂ lean loading of 0.2 mol_{CO₂}/mol_{MEA} is assumed, resulting in a specific reboiler duty (SRD) equal to 4.14 MJ/kg_{CO₂}. The equivalent electric power consumption, calculated using Eq. 1, is equal to 752.2 kWh/t_{CO₂}. The results on how different process modifications affect the energy consumption of the PCC process are represented in Fig. 2. For all of the investigated cases, the energy requirement in the reboiler for solvent regeneration is the largest contribution, covering at least 60% of the overall equivalent power consumption. The best case corresponds to the configuration with intercooled absorber, rich solvent split and LVC system together. This plant configuration, which consumes 18% less equivalent energy than the base case (617.4 kWh/t_{CO₂} vs 752.2 kWh/t_{CO₂}) due to the large savings in the steam used for the reboiler (i.e. 2.96 vs 4.14 GJ/t_{CO₂}), is expected to be demonstrated within the HERCCULES project.

It is worth noting that the results of the equivalent energy consumption for different plant configurations depend on the value for the equivalence ratio between thermal and electrical power and that, in any case, the selection of the most representative value for the electric power equivalent depends on the heat supply technology selected (e.g., heat pump, boiler, cogeneration cycle, etc.). An economic analysis is needed to determine the best option.

Table 2: Process simulation results for the base case from the Aspen Plus V14 model.

Main process simulation outcomes of the HERCCULES PCC pilot plant		
	Base case	Optimum case
Lean solvent flow rate, kg/h	2765	2074
L/G ratio, mol/mol	8.4	6.3
Rich solvent flow rate, kg/h	2949	2206
CO ₂ rich loading, mol _{CO₂} /mol _{MEA}	0.421	0.494
CO ₂ capture rate, %	95.2%	95.1%
Solvent temperature at stripper inlet, °C	111.5	93.2
Specific reboiler duty, MJ/kg _{CO₂}	4.14	2.96
Captured CO ₂ flow rate, kg/h	127	127
Specific equivalent work, kWh/t _{CO₂}	752.2	617.4

Fig. 2. Breakdown of the overall specific energy consumption of the capture process for the different PCC pilot plant configurations considered.

Conclusions

The process design of a pilot plant for post-combustion CO₂ capture from cement flue gases with 30%w MEA solution is described. The basis of design in terms of CO₂ capture efficiency and capacity, flue gas flow rate and specifications, solvent lean loading, together with the sizing of the main equipment is provided. A special focus is given on how process modifications and integration can affect the overall energy performance of the amine-based CO₂ capture system. This study has allowed the identification of the final plant configuration and to provide data for the plant design. Several process configurations have been investigated with Aspen Plus simulations. The breakdown of the energy penalty (evaluated with the equivalent electric power consumption) shows that the best case corresponds to the configuration which involves the intercooled absorber, the rich solvent split and the LVC system applied together. The standard post-combustion process without any modifications resulted in a specific reboiler duty of 4.14 GJ/tCO₂ and an equivalent electric consumption of 752 kWh/tCO₂. Compared to the base case, the optimized configuration is associated with a roughly 29% SRD reduction (2.96 GJ/tCO₂) and 18% decrease of the equivalent electric consumption (617 kWh/tCO₂).

The new data that will be gathered during the HERCCULES test campaigns (scheduled in 2025) will be used to optimize the process conditions (L/G, lean loading, etc.) for each configuration, as well as to further validate or refine the Aspen Plus model, assessing the benefits of the advanced process configuration that has been identified within the present investigation.

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